

Exploring Artificial Intelligence to Enhance Learning among Tertiary Institutions Students in Kaduna State

¹Ajiboye Stephen Ilesanmi, ²Ajiboye Helen Omowumi & ³Onilu Amos Bamidele

¹Department of Educational Psychology, School of General Studies, Federal University of Education Zaria, Kaduna state. omodape4sure@gmail.com

²Department of Arts and Social Sciences, Faculty of Education, Kaduna State University, Kaduna state. helen.omobaby@gmail.com

³Department of Arts and Social Sciences, Police Secondary School, Karau-Karau, Zaria Kaduna State. 08036069245. oniluamos1@gmail.com

Abstract

This study explored artificial intelligence in enhancing learning among higher-institution students in Kaduna State. This study adopted a survey research design. The population consisted of tertiary institutions in four metropolitan local government areas. This study used a sample size of four hundred (400) respondents. The Artificial Intelligence on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (AISAPQ) was adapted and validated by the experts with a reliability index of 0.87 used for data collection. This study was guided by one research question and one research hypothesis. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the research hypothesis. The results revealed that there was no significant relationship between the use of artificial intelligence in enhancing learning among higher institution students in Kaduna State, with a p-value of 0.000 at 0.05. It is recommended that artificial intelligence should be used to enhance learning activities among higher institution students in Kaduna State to enable them to come out with flying colours. The government should make available technology-enhancing materials for students' learning activities to achieve better learning outcomes. Higher institution management and lecturers should encourage the use of artificial intelligence among students in Kaduna State and across the length and breadth of the Nigerian nation.

Keywords
Exploring,
Artificial
Intelligence,
Tertiary,
Learning,
Students.

Introduction

Social media and artificial intelligence, in particular, play a significant role in determining where society swings. It has become a phenomenon as a learning discussion in our society today particularly among higher institution students due to its wide acceptance. It is an instrument that has come to stay in our society, used by all strata of education in Nigeria, and Kaduna State in particular. Suffice to say, social media could bring better learning due to its spread, speed and acceptance across all strata of society particularly among students. Artificial intelligence (AI), generally expressed by the general public as the ability of machines or computers to think and act as humans, represent effort towards computerized systems to imitate the human mind and

actions (Mohammed et'al 2024). In this respect, the basic definition of artificial intelligence can be expressed as the skill and imitation of human behaviour or mind by tools or programs (Ahmet et'al 2020). According to Ajemba (2025), it may be an illusion of the current structure that artificial intelligence will come within the computer format used at home. This can enter our lives through different functions and shapes. Muhammed, Farha and Mudasir (2024) sees artificial intelligence as the new electricity of this age. Artificial intelligence is a candidate to present as the basic building block of the Fifth Industrial Revolution by providing itself as a powerful factor in ensuring economic development with its potential. Bashiru (2024) points out that new forms of technology will fill our lives and captivate our

youth, and this may leave schools with no choice but to make room for them. AI in education refers to the use of artificial intelligence technologies, such as device learning and natural language processing, to enhance the learning experience (Alneyadi et al., 2023). It involves the use of algorithms that analyze data, identify patterns, and make predictions, enabling educators to personalize learning for each student. (Kingsley et al., 2024).

The potential benefits of using AI in education are significant and personalized learning. One of the most significant advantages of AI in education can lead to better student outcomes, as students can learn at their own pace and in a way that suits their learning style that could revolutionize higher education by enhancing responsiveness to 21st century challenges across various institutions. Special focus is placed on how AI will impact programs in institutions that prepare special educators and related service providers. AI's potential lies in personalized learning experiences, administrative task automation, and support for critical thinking skills (Alexandra, 2023). Furthermore, it could lead to improved learning outcomes and increased student engagement. AI can automate repetitive tasks, such as grading, data analysis, and administrative tasks, freeing up time for teachers and students to focus on more meaningful tasks. Improved student engagement: AI can help improve student engagement by providing interactive and engaging learning experiences. For example, chatbots and virtual assistants can make learning more fun and interactive, and adaptive learning technologies can help students stay engaged by presenting materials at their level of understanding. AI can analyze large amounts of data and provide insights into student performance, allowing teachers to better understand their students and tailor their instruction accordingly. This can lead to

improved learning outcomes and student performance.

Consequently, Mircea (2023) defined learning functionally as changes in behavior that result from experience or mechanistically as changes in the organism that result from experience. De Houwer et al. (2023) defined learning as ontogenetic adaptation, that is, as changes in the behavior of an organism that result from regularities in the environment of the organism. This functional definition not only solves the problems of other definitions but also has important advantages for cognitive learning research. Afzal et al. (2021) defined learning as an enduring change in behavioral mechanisms. Likewise, learning is a process that underlies behavior. He argues that learning should not be confused with the product of this process, that is, the change in behavior. The change in the organism that is assumed to lie at the core of learning is sometimes described at a very abstract level but sometimes also involve a specific mental process. Alexandra (2023) and Ahmet and Fahih (2020) stated that learning is seen as only one of many mechanisms that determine behavior. So, the paper bridged the knowledge gap as seen in the result outcome.

Many tertiary institutions in Kaduna State continue to rely on conventional teaching and learning methods, which may not adequately address the diverse needs and learning styles of the current students. Additionally, issues such as limited technological infrastructure, insufficient funding, lack of awareness, inadequate training for educators, and institutional resistance to change further hinder the effective adoption of AI in educational settings. This situation raises important question on the actual influence of AI on learning outcomes, student engagement, and instructional effectiveness in Kaduna State's tertiary institutions. Without empirical evidence and critical analysis, it remains unclear how AI is currently being utilized, what impact it has and what barriers must be

addressed to maximize its benefits for learners. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing learning among students in tertiary institutions in Kaduna State, with the aim of identifying opportunities, challenges, and strategies for more effective integration of AI into the region's higher education system.

Statement of the Problem

Despite significant advancements in educational technology globally, many tertiary institutions in Nigeria continue to rely heavily on traditional teaching methods that may not fully meet the evolving learning needs of students in the digital age. As the global academic landscape increasingly embraces artificial intelligence (AI) to personalize learning, automate administrative tasks, and enhance student engagement, Nigerian higher education institutions face challenges and effectively adopting and integrating these innovations. Therefore, artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force in the global education sector, offering innovative tools to enhance learning experiences, personalize instruction, and improve academic outcomes. However, in Kaduna State, Nigeria, the integration of AI technologies into tertiary education remains limited. While some institutions are beginning to explore the use of AI-driven tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, virtual assistants, and adaptive learning platforms, there is still a significant gap in understanding the extent of AI's influence on student learning within the region.

Objectives of the Study.

The following research objective will serve as a guide in this study.

1. To identify how artificial intelligence enhances learning among tertiary institution 'students' Kaduna state.

Research Questions

The following research question will serve as a guide in this study.

1. What is the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing learning among tertiary institutions students in Kaduna state?

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis was formulated and tested.

HO₁: There is no Significant Relationship between artificial intelligence and learning among tertiary institution students' in Kaduna state.

Methodology

The research design of the study was survey. This is a form of correlational design used when dealing with a systematic collection of data or information from a population or a sample of the population through the use of opinion scales and questionnaires. (Murphy, 2016). The population comprised students of the two tertiary institutions. The data for this study were collected using questionnaire. Purposive random sampling techniques was used to select two higher institutions, Kaduna State University and Kaduna Polytechnic, with a total population of 60,410. Kaduna State University has student population of 15,565, while Kaduna Polytechnic has a student population of 44,845 (Federal Ministry of Education 2017, Kaduna Polytechnic 2025). three hundred and eighty-one (381) respondents were selected for the study using research advisors (2006). This is because it represents the diverse nature of the students and their course of study.

The instrument for this study was a questionnaire structured in a five-point Likert scale model. The researcher adapted Artificial Intelligence on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (AISAPQ) designed by Mircea (2023). This was taken to experts in the department of educational psychology, Federal University of Education Zaria, Kaduna State, for their input, observations and corrections and were affected. Both face and content validity were established. Their observations and

corrections were affected, and approval of the corrected instruments served as proof of the validity of the instruments. Reliability, on the other hand, was ascertained by a pilot test of twenty (20) randomly selected respondents who were not part of the targeted research population. Cronbach reliability index of 0.87 was established for the instruments. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed to testing the hypotheses at 0.05 ($P < 0.05$).

Results

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis Between artificial intelligence and learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna State.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	Df	p-value
Artificial intelligence	381	35.07	4.17	.658	378	.000
Learning	381	35.99	4.15			

The table above shows that there is no statistically significant positive relationship between artificial intelligence and learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna State ($r = .658$, $df = 398$, $p < 0.05$). This means that the use of artificial intelligence and learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna State has no effect. Therefore, this hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

This study examined the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna. One research question and one research hypothesis were formulated in line with the objective of this study. Hypothesis one which states that there is a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna State, was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The results reveals that there is no significant relationship

in the role of artificial intelligence and learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna State, therefore, the hypothesis is hereby rejected. The findings of the study revealed that the respondents did not use artificial intelligence available and did not take advantage of artificial intelligence in their learning process to enhance performance in Kaduna State.

Ene (2025) examined the effect of Artificial Intelligence on the performance of students in tertiary institutions in Enugu State Urban 2015-2024. The study was carried out in two randomly selected tertiary institutions in Enugu State Urban: the University of Nigeria Enugu Campus (UNEC) and Enugu State University of Science and Technology. The study adopted a survey research design, and the population comprised 1308 students at 200 levels in both institutions. A total of 306 respondents were sampled using the Taro Yamani statistical formula. A simple percentage was employed for data analysis, and the chi-square test was used to test the hypotheses at a significant level of 0.05. The findings of the study revealed that, Artificial intelligence has a significant positive effect on students' active engagement in the teaching and learning process at the University of Nigeria Enugu Campus (UNEC) and Enugu State University of Science and Technology, and that AI has a significant positive effect on students' personalized learning experience at the University of Nigeria Enugu Campus (UNEC) and Enugu State University of Science and Technology. The above findings are in contrast with this study, which shows that there is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and learning in tertiary institutions among students in Kaduna State. This study bridged the location and population gaps.

The impact of artificial intelligence on the implementation of science education in tertiary institutions in Nigeria by Irunokhai et al. (2025) through a review of current

literature, especially journals, books, and notebooks, in both online publications and hard copies, and the major issues on the benefits of using AI for teaching and learning of science education in tertiary institutions. The study revealed that the integration of AI into the teaching and learning of science education in tertiary institutions in Nigeria supports personalization of the learning experience for students, data analysis tools, innovative teaching methods, effective assessment methods, support for different learning styles and needs, collaborative learning, and professional development. This study suggests that there is a need to integrate AI into the teaching and learning of education in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Kingsley et al. (2024) investigated the familiarity levels, perceived benefits, effectiveness, and challenges of using generative AI tools in computer science education, particularly to aid students' understanding of programming concepts. A total of 103 computer science students were surveyed, and the results were analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and one-sample t-tests. The findings indicated that students were moderately familiar with generative AI tools, with differences observed by the level of study. Students perceived ChatGPT as beneficial for enhancing their understanding and problem-solving skills, with statistically significant results supporting the positive influence of ChatGPT on learning outcomes. Additionally, Bashiru's (2024) study of ChatGPT was found to be effective in helping students comprehend and apply complex programming concepts to real-world problems. While students reported some challenges, including issues with accuracy and engagement, these were not statistically significant. This study identifies the need for awareness, training, and provision of digital tools that will enhance learning among tertiary institution students in Kaduna. This study bridged the methodological gap.

Conclusion

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into learning among tertiary institution students in Nigeria presents both transformative potential and critical challenges. AI technologies have significantly enhanced access to educational resources, enabled personalized learning, improved administrative efficiency, and facilitated innovative teaching methods. For students in Nigerian higher institutions, AI can bridge learning gaps, support diverse learning styles, and provide real-time feedback to foster academic growth. However, to fully realize these benefits, deliberate efforts must be made to address infrastructural deficits, digital literacy gaps, and policy constraints. Investment in digital infrastructure, training educators and students, and the development of ethical and inclusive AI policies are essential for sustainable implementation. Ultimately, the role of AI in Nigerian tertiary education is not just about adopting new technology but about reshaping the learning experience to be more adaptive, inclusive, and future-ready. Empirical evidence from Nigeria consistently shows that **AI holds substantial promise** in enhancing learning in tertiary institutions through personalization, engagement, skill development, and administrative improvements. However, challenges that are part of the gap to be bridged by future researchers remain substantial: infrastructure, training, equity, privacy, and ethics all demand immediate attention.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the recommendations are as follows:

1. The government should provide more funding to tertiary institutions so they can purchase AI tools to support teaching and research programs.
2. Both lecturers and students need to receive proper training on how to use AI to enhance teaching and learning.

References

- Afzal, S.M & Md, A.K (2021) Teaching and Learning Process to Enhance Teaching Effectiveness: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Humanities and Innovation*. 4 (1), 5.
- Ahmet, G. & Fahih A. (2020) Artificial Intelligence in Education and Schools. *Journal of Research on Education and Media*. 12 (1), 14.
- Ajemba, H.E (2025) Artificial Intelligence and Implementation of Science Education in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. *American Journal of Education and Evaluation Studies*. 2 (6), 54.
- Alexandra, H. (2023) Role of AI In Education Injuriy: *Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanity*. 2 (3), 360.
- Alneyadi, S. W., F. A. Q. & Abu-Al-Aish, A. (2023). The Effect of using Smart e-learning app on the Academic Achievement of Eighth-grade . London. Gate Print
- Bashiru, A.G (2024) Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Distance Education at Sokoto State Tertiary Institutions: A pathway to Enhanced Learning. *World Journal of Innovation and Modern Technology*. 8 (3), 103.
- Ene, S. (2025) Effects of Artificial Intelligence on the Performance of Students in Tertiary Institutions in Enugu state Urban 2015-2024. *Journal of Policy and Development Studies*. 17 (2), 54.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2017). Total Enrolment (Undergraduate and Post-graduate) <https://education.gov.ng>
- Gningue, S. M., Peach, R., Jarrah, A. M. & Wardat, Y. (2022). The Relationship between AI and Learning Habit among Students in Urban Areas. Caracas. Soso Press
- Ibrahim, H. K, A., Noor, A. M., Samad, Z. W. & Hamza, M. (2022). Covid-19 Pandemic and Its Impact on Psychological Distress, Malignancy and Chronic Diseases: A Scoping Review. *Eduvest-Journal Of Universal Studies*, 2(5),. 1017–1021.
- Irunokhai, E.A., Adigun, J.O., Dada, O.S., Adeniji, O.A., Wealth, S.A., Onihunwa, J.O., Meduna, P.N., Jeje, C.A., James, Z. & Irunokhai, B.O. (2025) Outcome of Computer Science Students in Tertiary Institutions in New Busa Metropolis, Niger state, Nigeria. *Dutse Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*. 10 (4), 25.
- Jan De Houwer, Dermot, B. Mow, A. (2023) What is Learning? On the Nature and Merits of a Functional Defination of Learning. *Psychonomic Bulletin and Review. Journal of jurisdictional claims in Education*. 12, (3), 749.
- Jarrah, A. M., Almassri, H. J. J. & Wardat, Y. (2022). Assessing the impact of digital games-based learning on students' performance in learning fractions using (ABACUS) software application. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 18(10), 159.
- Kaduna Polytechnic (2025) Key Institutional Data. <https://kadunapoly.edu.ng>
- Kingsley, E., Abiola, M.S & Nwafor, A.C (2024) Artificial Intelligence, Teaching and Research Programmes in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence*. 1 (1), 28.
- Mircea, M. (2023) Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Education. Research Association for Interdisciplinary Studies. *Journal of jurisdictional claims in Education*. 12, (3), 749.
- Muhammed, T., Farha, D.H & Mudasir, R.S (2024) Role of Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Conceptual Review. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 22 (1), 14.
- Murphy, M., (2016). Population Definitions for Comparative Surveys in Education. Australia. Camber Well Press. .2248.